

Technology for Assessing the Quality of Jumping in Volleyball Players and the Methodology for its Development

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Abstract:

In the article, the methodology for the development of saccharification abilities of 19-21-year-old volleyball players is scientifically based.

Keywords: jumping, jumping endurance, jumping technique, vertical jump from place to place, competition cycles, jumping exercise, jumping coordination.

INTRODUCTION.

Law No. 637 of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on education" of September 23, 2020, Law No. 76-II of the "on Physical Education and sports" of May 26, 2000, PQ No. 3031 on measures for the further development of Physical Education and mass sports of June 3, 2017, Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on measures to radically improve the system of Public Administration in the field of Physical Education and sports" dated March 5, 2018, decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on measures to widely implement a healthy lifestyle and further develop mass sports" dated October 30, 2020, decree PF 6099 and decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 19, 2020 also, the tasks set in the decisions of the outgoing government on physical education and sports, the most pressing issue in all educational institutions today, the strengthening of the movement of physical education and sports among the civilian population, increasing its popularity, including organizing and conducting physical education and sports training through new methods and means to educate the younger generation in all educational, more focused on the continuous involvement and development of student - youth in sports activities in public and the organization of mass-sports events.

MAIN STORY.

As a result of visual observation of a large number of volleyball training, training in volleyball and analysis of the processes of training volleyball players, it is noticeable that when applying exercises for the formation of jump-played playing methods, the jump in accordance with these methods does not seriously focus on the kinematic and coordination elements and phases of turininig. Such an idea arises that the concepts of jumping, jumping, and jumping endurance do not specialize according to the technique of play methods, which are performed as if jumping, but rather look at these concepts with homogeneous meaning-content and coordination characteristics. It is on this principle that the training and formation of jump types is carried out. It is of paramount practical importance when teaching jump execution game methods, preparing to jump from place to place or running in the development of jumping and jumping endurance, actively moving hands in an arc-like Direction (back-bottom up) and generating inertial force, debsinking, maintaining the necessary coordination-technique in the air (at the base position), performing the appropriate game method, It is assumed that the use of a number of block-templates developed by us for the effective organization of this process will give a positive result.

The techniques, coordination, and kinematic elements of full (maximum height) jumps used in rapid moving shots, hurdling, ball passing, including ball passing, from different zones are completely different from each other. Therefore, the exercises used to train and improve play methods that can be played by jumping from different zones should be modeled based on the resistance tactics of a particular opposing team or opposing player. It is important to emphasize the kinematic elements, phases, biomechanical laws of the jump type taught in this regard and the technique of its execution. In other words, it is darcor to pay serious attention to the technique, even the tactics, of performing it when teaching jump types. In the selection of candidates in accordance with volleyball clubs, volleyball clubs and national teams, and during training sessions, specialist trainers pay special attention to such physical qualities as jumping ability, jumping ability and jumping endurance. But not all trainers will always be able to use effective exercises in the development of these abilities and qualities, and it is not accepted as a serious matter to evaluate them using tests in accordance with the dynamics of formation (growth). However, training in jumping skills, choosing targeted exercises in the development of jumping and jumping endurance, regularly controlling (evaluating) the dynamics of the development of these qualities makes it possible to effectively organize this process.

Taking into account these pressing problems, we have organized a number of studies on volleyball players of different ages and sports training.

Volleyball was attended by 19-21-year-old children who have been engaged in a specialized sports school for 2 years:

The following kinematic elements of vertical jumping from place to place were studied using a special tool-device:

- jump height based on active movement of two hands(classic option);
- jump height based only on the active movement of the right hand (the left hand connects to the body);
- jump height based only on the active movement of the left hand (the right hand connects to the body);
- jump height without active movement of two hands (both hands are tied to the body);
- jump height based on debugging only with the right foot;
- jump height based on debugging with left foot only;

And with the help of modified tests, the maximum number of times of rapid sit-ups (explosive strength of the right and left legs) on the right and left legs is a.

The results of the study showed that the height of the vertical jump from a classical variant place is a symmetrical execution of a number of kinematic elements that provide jumpiness, the strength of the right and left foot (explosive force) is equally developed, while the debugging is inextricably linked to the synchronously active movement of the right and left hand (their inertial movement) during the jump. In particular, it was found that the height of the vertical jump from the place, standing on the platform, is based on the explosive strength of the legs-posture-head forward, moving the left behind arms back and forth at the same speed, bending the legs at an optimal angle and non-linear feet. The fact that these kinematic factors have different “strength” in study participants, in which the height of the jump in a large range (22 cm.) led to recording (Table 1). Kinematic factors (functional movement of jumping elements) in the most weakly formed controller, the jump height is 31 cm., while the relatively “strongly” shaped examiner is 5-3 CM. represented by. The average statistical indicator (χ) is 43.6 CM. founded ni. Due to the large difference (range) of minimum and maximum pointers, the mean quadratic deviation (σ) of the mean pointer was also differentiated by a large amount (4.32).

Table 1. Pointers (n=16) that represent the height of the vertical jump from the place and the role of some of the kinematic factors that provide it in 19-21 year old volleyball players

Vertical jump conditions	Results obtained	
	min – max	$\bar{\chi} \pm \sigma$
Vertical jump from place to place on the platform (CM)	31 – 53	43,6±4,32
Jump only on the basis of active movement of the right hand (CM)	28 – 47	38,2±3,28
Jump only based on the active movement of the left hand (CM)	25 – 46	38,2±3,28
Jump without active movement of two hands (CM)	25 – 46	18,2±3,16
Just jump in the right leg with a kiss (CM)	27 – 39	32,8±3,74
Jumping only on the left leg with a kiss (CM)	29 – 43	37,2±3,22

Only on the basis of the active movement of the right hand (inertial movement) is recorded the height of the vertical jump from the place min pointer 28 cm., max pointer 47 cm. founded ni. This display range (diapozoni) is 19 cm. was equivalent to. The average statistical indicator is 38.2±3.28 cm. It can be seen that the height of the vertical jump from the place determined in the traditional order is 43.6±4.32 CM. the vertical jump height recorded on the basis of the active movement of the right hand only when the left hand is attached to the body is 38.2±3.28 CM. founded ni. So, the height of the jump is 5.2 cm with the “elimination” of a single kinematic factor. ga declined.

Only on the basis of the active movement of the left hand, the vertical jump height from the place (the right hand is connected to the body) is 35.4±4.02 CM. was equivalent to. Jump height in the traditional order is 12.2 cm. ga was expressed in small quantities.

The jump height recorded only on the basis of the active movement of the right hand is 3 from the jump height performed with the active movement of the left hand sm.ga over. Therefore, it can be confidently noted that the asymmetric difference in the active movement of the hands performed during the debugging time for jumping was also confirmed by the intermediate diaposons between the minimum and maximum results of individual indicators.

Chunonchi, diaposon 19 between min and max indicators of jump height observed on the basis of active movement of the right hand sm.ga, left hand movement jump pointers diaposoni 21 sm.ni organized.

The results of this test showed that the test-volleyball players involved in the study had a minimum jump height (14 cm.) and maximum (25 cm.) displays a large diapason (11 cm.) with distinction. It is possible that such a large diapasonic difference is justified by the fact that in volleyball players involved in the study, the leg muscles have different explosive strength.

The average indicator of the height of the jump with the arms tied is 18.2 CM. was equivalent to. Hence, the height of the jump without the help of hands is in the traditional order from the height of the jump (43.6 CM.) 25.4 cm. distinguished by a small amount.

The results obtained on the tests of jumping with the help of hands, but separately on the right leg, separately on the left leg, showed that the explosive strength of the legs is asymmetric in nature. In particular, the height of the debsinib jump on the right leg is on average 32.8 ± 3.74 CM. with a jump of 37.2 ± 3.22 CM in the left leg, while a jump of 37.2 ± 3.22 CM in the left leg. was equivalent to. It can be seen that when jumping vertically from place to place, the legs bend and write synchronously, it turns out that the explosive strength of the left leg is stronger than that of the right leg. It can be confidently noted that the explosive strength of the right and left leg was when it was well developed in a symmetrical ratio, with a vertical jump height of 43.6 CM. it was clear that it would be higher when not encouraged.

From the recorded pattern of pointers, it is possible to come to such a hulosa that the active movement of the hands (inertial movement) at the time of the jump, when the explosive strength of the legs was ensured to form in a symmetrical order, both vertical jump from the place and running and jumping would be represented by much higher pointers.

The fact that the explosive strength of the legs developed in an asymmetric ratio was also confirmed by the results of separate maximum speed on the right and left leg and maximum standing tests (Table 5). The Chunonchi, sitting on the right leg test had a minimum pointer of 3 times and a maximum pointer of 16 times. The diapason of these displays was 13 times. The average statistical indicator, on the other hand, was represented by 6.5 ± 2.4 times.

The maximum speed on the left leg and the maximum number of times per sitting was 5-15 times, and the diapason of the indicators was 10 times. The average statistical indicator was 8.8 ± 2.9 times. So it turns out that the explosive strength of the left foot is higher than that of the right foot. Even from the results of these tests, explosive force asymmetry is clearly thrown apart.

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